

Time-Volume Training™ by Nick Nilsson

Time Volume Training Review

Time Volume Training is a muscle-building program hinged on workout density rather than intensity, more volume in a time block than muscle failure. Keep reading my review because this is going to be interesting.

When I first came across this program, I could not help but think of old-school volume strategies like the 8×8 workout system from the 50s by the late iconic American bodybuilding guru Vince Gironda or the similar 10×10 German Volume Training from the 70s by Rolf Feser, later adopted by Canadian strength coach legend Charles Poliquin.

These programs, including the Time Volume Training program reviewed here, share one common factor: developing progressive overload and muscle gains by increasing the total workload rather than increasing the load intensity (increasing the weight).

Who Is Nick Nilsson?

Nick Nilsson is also known as “the mad scientist” when it comes to his approach to building muscle. He is a very well respected personal trainer and bodybuilder. In addition Nick has written articles for Men’s Fitness, Muscle & Fitness and a lot more publications.

He is an authority figure in the fitness industry and is in fantastic shape for his age, as evidenced in the picture below. He clearly knows what works when it comes to building muscle. His methods may be very controversial but they deliver results. Results are all that matter.

Training Density

The program focuses a lot on manipulating a variable called “training density”. Training density is essentially a measure of how much work you do in a certain timeframe.

For instance, if you bench press 100kg for 30 reps in 10 minutes, then your training density will be 300kg per minute. If on your next session you manage a training density of 325kg per min then your training density has increased. This means you have also increased your overall workload – this will result in your body responding to that stimulus and building more muscle!

Magic Of The Number Three

Three reps is the magic number in this program by Nick Nilsson. You will be performing an exercise within a 15 minute block of time. You should select a weight that you can do at least 10 reps with.

Start by doing a set of 3 reps, then stop and rest for 10 seconds. Then do another set of 3 reps and stop and rest for 10 seconds. Continue in this fashion until you the third rep is a struggle, but don't take it to failure.

Then increase the rest time to 20 seconds and repeat this protocol again with sets of 3 reps. Keep going until you can't get 3 good reps, then increase the rest time to 30 seconds and repeat the protocol. If you have to increase the rest time to 40 seconds

then do it – keep going until the 15 minute total block of time is up.

This approach of doing 3 reps with short rest times in a short window is a great way of building up training volume in an intelligent and fast way. When you are more fresh at the start you will be performing more reps with less rest time (front-loading). As you tire then you will be performing less reps with more rest.

This is also a great way to ensure that form breakdown doesn't take place. You won't be going to complete failure and therefore you will also be reducing injury risk. This is a perfectly safe way to train as long as you are using proper form.

This approach is known as the “standard” form of Time-Volume Training. However, in the complete program you get 13 variations of hypertrophy training such as Mechanical Drop TVT, Hybrid TVT, Closed-Chain TVT, etc. You also get 6 targeted versions of TVT for building strength like Countdown TVT, Wave Loading TVT, etc. Nick also has bodyweight TVT for mass for those who have no training equipment.

Building In Progressive Overload

In order to build more muscle you have to induce progressive overload in your training. So how does this program do this? I will explain this now.

It is very simple, if you can make it 1/3 of the way through the total 15 minute time block on 10 seconds rest then you would increase the weight in the next workout. If you don't then keep the weight the same. Just keep repeating this process over time.

Benefits Of Time-Volume Training

Here are the benefits of Time-Volume Training, whether you have exercise equipment or not. It doesn't matter if you train at home or at a gym:

- Builds Muscle Easily – Your body will adapt to the volume based overload by building muscle
- Improves Your Base Strength – This program improves your base strength on the exercise that you are performing and will carry over to a higher max lift.
- Low Stress On The Body – Won't run you into the ground or spike your cortisol levels. No rep is taken to complete failure ensures that your nervous system is not taxed too much.
- Improves Strength And Endurance – Improves your endurance and ability to sustain high levels of strength over a longer period of time. This can be especially useful to those who work manual jobs.
- Works For People Of All Levels – Whether you are an advanced lifter or complete noob this program is adaptable to all levels.
- Perform Movements More Efficiently – As you are getting in so much practice with multiple 3 rep sets and greasing the groove your exercise technique and efficiency will improve.
- Great For Fat Loss – This program can help you shred up really well at the same time as packing on more muscle. The rest times are short and will force you to work your aerobic system constantly for the entire workout.

Conclusion

To conclude, in this article I have examined Time-Volume Training by Nick Nilsson. I am personally very impressed by this training system and the results that it has delivered to lots of different people. It is a training system that is completely different and works very well.

Nick is very knowledgeable in the fitness industry and is very well respected. His unconventional techniques do have a track record of delivering real results.

I believe his Time-Volume Training is definitely worth investing in if you want to build muscle and burn fat at the same time and take your physique to the next level. If you are working out with minimal equipment or restricted equipment then this system is perfect as well for your needs.